

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
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IMPROVING PATIENT SATISFACTION WITH MEDICATION INSTRUCTIONS:
A PILOT STUDY

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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May 2015

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ABSTRACT

Patient satisfaction with healthcare is being used as one indicator to determine Medicare reimbursement rates to healthcare facilities. Patient satisfaction with hospital care may be linked to a patient's ability to manage self care. Furthermore, in the outpatient surgical environment, providing adequate education in a way that meets patient's needs is challenging. The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice project was to use existing evidence to implement and evaluate a one page simplified narcotic medication instruction sheet in a local hospital's outpatient surgical department in an effort to increase patient satisfaction scores by 20%. Patient satisfaction scores were gathered for randomly selected patients discharged from the outpatient surgery department during November and December 2014; scores were evaluated to determine whether the new medication instructions affected satisfaction. In this pilot project, the sample consisted of 10 patients who did not receive the instruction sheet and 10 patients who did. There was no significant difference in average satisfaction score between the two groups. There was also no significant correlation found between patient age, gender, and days to contact on satisfaction scores. Future studies should evaluate whether providing narcotic medication instructions in multiple languages and conducting the study over a longer period of time lead to significant changes in satisfaction.

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

There are a number of people who have helped in the research and completion of this project that I would like to acknowledge. First, I would like to thank Dr. Beth Keely for her time, guidance, support, and expertise in the formulation and completion of my project. Second, I would like to thank Dr. Catherine Cummins for her work as a second chair and reader who gave great insight into areas of the project I could not have seen. Dr. Hojin Moon was instrumental in evaluating and incorporating his statistical knowledge and assistance into the analysis and results section of the project.

I would like to use this opportunity to thank the most important people in my life who have enabled me to reach my goals. My mom, Ellen, and my father, Horst, have spent their whole lives teaching me to dream big, never settle for mediocre, and reach for the stars. They came from Germany to seek out opportunities in America after the war. Their stories of how they have gotten to where they are today have inspired me. I would not have been able to complete this project and my education without their never-ending support and love.

I would also like to recognize my children Shane and Ryan Nunez whom I love very much. Through this process, they had to understand that their mom was stressed, sleepless, and emotional but loved and supported my efforts anyway. I sought the Doctoral degree not only for personal benefit but also to show my boys that education is an invaluable asset. I would like to thank my dear friends, Kristen Geirman, Katie

Pennington, Jennifer Allen, and Arnold Coston, whom all provided me with the downtime and support in order to refocus on my goal at times when I was lost. A special thank you to Antoinette van Schijndel, who without her support, friendship, and compassion, I would never have been able to complete my project.

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BACKGROUND

Evaluating patient satisfaction is a key performance measure that is determining payment for performance plans by the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) and private insurance plans. Hospitals must participate in the Hospital Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems (HCAHPS) to avoid a 2 percent reduction in payment for services (Kutney-Lee et al., 2009). The Tax Relief and Healthcare Act of 2006 mandated the HCAHPS program would extend to include the outpatient surgical component, laboratory services, radiology services and emergency services. CMS sought information from facilities that provide outpatient surgery in order to guide the development and design of a survey measuring patient-reported outcomes. The program was started in 2010 and mirrors the data collected for inpatient services. Identical to the HCAHPS requirement, hospitals will have to report data to the Hospital Outpatient Quality Reporting program (Hospital OQR) to ensure they receive full payment through the Outpatient Perspective Payment System (OPPS) for services such as outpatient surgery, emergency services, laboratory services, radiology services and observation services.

The incorporation of the HCAHPS and Hospital OQR into the prospective payment system, pay-for-performance (P4P) plans, and quality programs has highlighted the value of monitoring and reporting patient satisfaction as an important part of value based healthcare (Kutney-Lee et al., 2009). Previous research which studied patient satisfaction in outpatient surgery identified satisfaction with anesthesia care, doctor communication, provision of discharge instructions, and pain management all have an effect on the patient's perception of care (Lemos et al., 2009). Research has also

discerned that demographic factors, such as gender and age, can impact patient satisfaction scores (Hekkert, Cihangir, Kleefstra, Van den Berg, & Kool, 2009). Prior research also identified that the manner of delivery and the quantity of information delivered can affect a patient's perception of quality of care (Fagermoen & Hamilton, 2006).

Problem Statement

Patient satisfaction at a Los Angeles area hospital outpatient surgery department was the focus of this pilot study. The current electronic medical record (EMR) system is Cerner. Cerner is a data base type program in which hospital systems can document patient care. Another feature of Cerner is the ability to gather patient care data and analyze the care delivered through quality improvement activities. Within the Cerner EMR program there is a discharge/depart program that provides nursing staff the ability to print disease specific, surgical specific, and medication specific patient instructions. Cerner is linked to a program called ExitCare for surgical and disease specific discharge instructions and a program called Multum for medication specific patient instructions. When an order for discharge is present in the patient's EMR, the nurse goes to the depart screen and chooses the surgical or disease specific discharge instructions and the medication specific information for any new prescriptions that prints with the physician's orders. The result is anywhere from 10-40 pages of information which is sent home with the patient. The expectation of the nurse is to review all pages with the patient. The nurse is to highlight specific areas for the patient related to possible complications of their surgical procedure and potential side effects of medications. Not only is this a

cumbersome task, but the nurses were not trained how to find the information in the packet.

This hospital also collects and reports data to evaluate the patient's satisfaction with their discharge instructions with a program called Outpatient Surgery Patient Satisfaction Measurement System (OP Surgery PSMS). The hospital system uses a division of their corporation to randomly survey 25 patients from the outpatient surgical department about their experience during their surgical care and the surveys are conducted in Spanish and English. The selection criteria is based on their patient type (OP), hospital service code (57), and clinic code (OS). Patients are specifically asked "Before giving you any new medicine, how often did hospital staff tell you what the medicine was for and describe possible side effects in a way you could understand?" Both questions are rated on a 4-point Likert scale from never to always including the options of "do not know" and "refused."

Historically, the outpatient surgical department obtained scores ranging from 33-80% satisfaction in these two areas. It has been difficult to isolate any one direct cause to the variation in scores received and the manner in which the hospital system calculates the percentage of satisfaction. The PSMS score is calculated by only counting patients who scored the questions with an always, 4, and dividing that number by all patients who answered the question. This method of computation is falsely recording the percentage of satisfaction by discounting all other scores from patients who have reported or answered with other than always. The facility is unable to identify small, yet important success in improving patient satisfaction. It is theorized by this author that the scores remain low in this area because of the magnitude of informational papers provided to

patients which prevents nursing staff from focusing on the important aspects of the instruction.

Purpose Statement

Thus, the purpose of this quality improvement pilot study is to implement measures to improve the process of providing discharge instructions to increase patient satisfaction scores by 20%.

Supporting Framework

A theoretical framework provides a foundation for the planning and implementation of a project to ensure its ultimate success. The theoretical framework chosen for this project is the United States Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI) Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) model (Powell, Rushmer, & Davies, 2009) (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. The plan-do-study-act cycle.

This model was developed from earlier quality improvement approaches called the Model for Improvement and Shewhart's Plan-Do-Check-Act tool (Powell et al., 2009). The basis for the PDSA comes from systems theory which suggests that systems are made up of interacting interdependent elements (Powell et al., 2009). These systems are unpredictable and non-linear which result in changes that are small but can have large consequences. The PDSA approach uses short-cycle, small-scale tests, reflection on the process and reflection of the effects of the actions. The key advantage of this PDSA model is that it enables healthcare teams to learn quickly because they take action, observe the effects, and make changes. PDSA changes are typically small, take minimal time and require minimal financial investment (Powell et al., 2009).

The PDSA cycle has four stages of involvement. The first stage is to develop a plan and define the objectives and is called the plan (plan). The second stage is carrying out the plan and collecting the data (do). The third stage is when the data is analyzing and summarizing what was learned (study). The fourth and final stage is where the researcher is planning the next cycle with the necessary modifications (act) (Gillam & Siriwardena, 2013). For the purpose of this study, the first stage is developing a plan for improving patient satisfaction scores related to discharge medication instructions. This is where the author plans the change to be tested and/or implemented and predicts what may happen and why. This will be outlined in the methods section for this project. The second stage, do, is implementing the new medication discharge instructions for the patients. The third phase is the study section where the data is evaluated before the change and after the change. Patient satisfaction scores in this specific area were evaluated and documented. In this section of the framework, the researcher will reflect

on the process and identify what was learned and will summarize the effect the change in discharge medication instructions had on patient satisfaction scores. The last stage will be to plan and determine what, if any, changes need to be made to the original plan of the study. This is where the author will determine to fully implement the change of one or more successful changes and start the cycle again to evaluate these changes (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. The plan-do-study-act cycle applied to project.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

A literature review was completed by utilizing the California State University Fullerton library. Search engines, including CINAHL and PubMed were queried for data between the years of 2000 to 2014. The key variables searched were discharge instructions, medication instructions, patient satisfaction and demographic variables. Patient satisfaction was narrowed down to information related to hospitalized patients, outpatient surgery and perception. Medication instructions were narrowed to short stay discharge, medication instructions and perceptions of discharge instructions. A table of evidence (see Appendix C) provides a detailed list of the key research articles discussed.

Discharge Instructions

Discharge instructions are often misunderstood by patients recently discharged from hospitals because of the amount of information given and the process by which the information is delivered (Louis-Simonet et al., 2004). Structured discharge interviews, in which caregivers take the time to explain each item, increased the patient's knowledge of instructions and their acknowledgement of receipt (Louis-Simonet et al., 2004). Providing defined content of discharge instructions within the teaching plan can increase the knowledge of patients whose experience is limited (Maloney & Weiss, 2008). Surgical specific discharge instructions, along with medication specific instructions, will improve patient understanding of the content provided (Zavala & Shaffer, 2011). Providing clear and concise discharge instructions improve patient outcomes, satisfaction, pain control, self-care and compliance with follow-up visits (Ben-Morderchai, Herman, Kerzman, & Irony, 2010). Research has found information is

poorly distributed to patients in the admission and discharge process (Lithner & Zilling, 2000). Patients are given too much information at admission and not enough at discharge and the relevancy of information can save time and money.

Medication Instructions

Surprisingly, after discharge, only 30% of patients report being educated regarding their new or continued medications (Louis-Simonet et al., 2004). Patients required counseling of medication but the key factor is to ensure the patient's understanding via written instructions and verifying their acknowledgement (Kerzman, Baron-Epel, & Toren, 2005). New innovations within electronic medical records allow hospitals to connect medication instructions to the discharge information provided to patients. Research has shown that medication instructions imbedded into the discharge information does not increase patient medication knowledge base and is ineffectual in decreasing readmission rates (Showalter, Rafferty et al., 2011). Borgsteede, Karapinar-Carkit, Hoffmann, Zoer, and van den Bemt (2011) studied the difference of written discharge medication instruction versus one on one counseling of the instructions and determined that patients prefer both written and oral counseling of information in order to discern their specific needs.

Patient Satisfaction

The Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services ranks hospitals regarding the patient's satisfaction with discharge instructions and instructions regarding the use of medications. Satisfaction with instructions are varied dependent on the manner in which the instructions are provided. In a study by Hekkert, Cihangir, Kleefstra, van den Berg, and Kool (2009), satisfaction rates had more to do with the case mix more than the

information provided and that hospital systems needed to identify case mix when comparing satisfaction scores across a specific healthcare system. Furthermore, studies have concluded that a structured system to provide discharge or medication instructions improved patient satisfaction scores (Ben-Morderchai et al., 2010).

Demographic Variables

Patient mix or variables are a factor that is hard to be ignored in relation to satisfaction and understanding of the discharge information provided. Maloney and Weiss (2008) completed a study in which patients whose cultural origin was reported as non-white or experience with exposure to hospital systems was limited, required more detailed and complete explanation of discharge and medication instructions. The age of a patient affects their comprehension and satisfaction with instructions received at discharge (Hekkert et al., 2009). A study by Sitzia and Wood (1997) found that a consistent determinant of satisfaction is related to the patient's age. The older the patient, the higher the reported satisfaction with medical care. Studies have reported that the patient's age, level of education and their current health status are important determinants of satisfaction and that the age of a patient has the highest correlation to satisfaction than any other factor (Hekkert et al., 2009). According to Maloney and Weiss (2008), females, verses males, require and request more information at discharge.

METHODS

Prior to commencement of the research project, Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was sought by the California State University, Long Beach IRB. Patient confidentiality was maintained by utilizing a coded unique identifier in the collection of data.

The setting is a for-profit hospital located in Los Angeles County which is part of a 75 hospital system across the United States. The hospital has 167 licensed beds and does not care for trauma patients. The outpatient surgical unit is comprised of an 8 bed unit. The average monthly volume of outpatient surgeries is 180 per month. The outpatient surgical unit is staffed with 6 full time employees and at times of increased volume, employees from other outpatient units are floated to the department.

A staff meeting was held by the unit manager to describe the project. The narcotic medication instructions provided by the Cerner Multum program were then substituted with the one page, simplified, narcotic medication instruction sheet and the side effects of the medication were highlighted by the nurse discharging the patient (see Attachment A). The nurse reviewed the narcotic medications and described the side effects with the patient in the usual manner that was done prior to the implementation of the project. All patients for the two months during the project were given their new narcotic medication instructions in this manner.

Sample Methods

The patients were randomly selected from the discharge population based on specific criteria outlined by the hospital's PSMS guidelines. The first step in patient collection was to identify the patient type "OS" for outpatient surgery coded in the

record. Hospital service codes for the outpatient population were then pulled if the service code was 57 (outpatient). The patients were contacted from this list and they were called in order of surgical date until a total of 25 patients had been queried.

A quantitative paradigm method was used to collect data related to outpatient surgical patient's responses to information related to discharge medication information. The facility's existing method of post-operative telephone interview and scoring system were utilized to gather the patient's scoring system. Highly structured questions designed by the facility's patient satisfaction measurement system (PSMS) were used and not modified. The data collected during the two month period of the study were gathered to collect each patient's specific score.

A multiple regression method was run with two variables. The condition of pre change and post change and another taking into account the covariates of age, gender, and time between procedure and contact in days. Logistic regression was used to compare the facility's satisfaction score and the regression statistical scores.

Proposal Project

The goal of this project was to increase the patient's individual ratings related to medication instructions and the level to which the side effects were described and understood. Patient specific response scores from September and October 2014 were used as a baseline score. The goal of the project was to increase the specific percentage scores by 20%. The patients of the outpatient surgical department were given a one page information sheet on narcotic pain relievers (see Appendix A) with information related to side effects for each new narcotic pain medication prescribed by their physician prior to discharge. The surgical specific instructions were not changed in this project. The time

frame for the project was a period of 60 days and all patients discharged through the same day surgical unit who were prescribed narcotics were included. Nursing provided the medication informational documents and highlighted the side effects of all new narcotic medication prescribed to the patients. Nursing then asked the patient to locate the side effects on their medication education and asked them to read them and recite what they had learned. All discharge instruction documents were stapled together and sent home with the patient in the usual manner.

Data collection was completed by hospital system. The data was extracted from the published monthly results. A calculation was drawn to identify a true statistical value and this value was compared to the two prior months to identify if a change occurred.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

At the conclusion of the project period, the data was collected and compiled for statistical analysis. The R project for statistical computing was used for data analysis. The purpose of the analysis was to determine if a change in patient satisfaction scores had occurred for the two questions in the survey. The data was examined for age, gender, days to contact, question 1 scores and question 2 scores for both pre and post groups. Data with missing variables were excluded from computation (see Table 1).

Table 1

Summary of Dataset

Group	Age	Gender	Days to Contact	Question 1	Question 2
A	43	M	9	4	4
A	19	F	11	4	3
A	71	M	9	4	4
A	77	F	24	1	1
A	72	M	9	4	4
A	42	F	14	4	4
A	55	M	35	4	4
A	70	M	38	4	3
A	73	F	44	4	4
A	N/A	N/A	43	4	2
B	20	M	13	4	3
B	29	M	8	4	4
B	39	F	13	4	1
B	65	M	19	4	2
B	60	F	10	1	3
B	5	F	24	4	4
B	86	M	26	4	N/A
B	N/A	N/A	12	4	N/A
B	N/A	N/A	16	4	4
B	N/A	N/A	16	4	1

Note. N/A = not applicable, not answered.

The pre-intervention group (group A) was comprised of 10 patients. There were 4 (40%) females and 5 (50%) males with 1 (10%) patient who declined to report both age and gender. The sample ranged from 19 to 77 years of age and the mean age was 58 years. The mean days to contact was 23.6 days.

The post-intervention group (group B) consisted of 10 patients. There were 3 (30%) females and 4 (40%) males with 3 (30%) patients who declined to report both age and gender. The sample ranged from 5 to 86 years of age and the mean age was 43 years. The parent for the 5 year old patient reported the answers to question 1 and question 2 and those results were recorded using the child's age. The mean days to contact was 15.7 days.

The average mean scores and standard deviations for questions 1 and 2 were calculated for both pre and post reports. The results for question 1 showed no variability as seen in Table 2. The results for question 2 showed variability from 3.3 mean in the pre group A and 2.75 in the post group B as seen in Table 3.

Table 2

Summary by Pre and Post Question 1

Pre/Post	n	Mean	Median	sd
Pre	10	3.7	4	0.95
Post	10	3.7	4	0.95

Note. N = sample size, SD = standard deviation.

Table 3

Summary by Pre and Post Question 2

Pre/Post	n	Mean	Median	sd
Pre	10	3.3	4	1.06
Post	10	2.75	3	1.28

Note. N = sample size, SD = standard deviation.

A two-tailed Welch's t-test (or Welch-Aspin Test) was run to compare whether there were any significant differences between the pre and post responses to question 2 because there were unequal sample sizes and an unequal variance. The test was not done on question 1 because the results showed almost no variability. Significance was set at 0.05. The result was a t value = 0.976, the degrees of freedom = 13.586, the p-value = 0.3461 with a 95 % confidence interval with LL of -0.66 and an UL of 1.76. There were no significant differences between the pre and post answers to questions 2, $p > 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, which was that there was no difference between the satisfaction scores of question 2 from pre and post segments.

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) approach was done to test mean differences between the test scores (see Table 4). There were no significant differences between all variables from pre to post patient satisfaction scoring values.

Table 4

Results of Variance by Multiple Variables for Question 2

Variable	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr (>F)
Pre/Post	1	1.344	1.344	1.219	0.291
Age	1	1.818	1.818	1.648	0.223
Pre/Post	1	1.344	1.344	1.181	0.299
Gender	1	1.394	1.394	1.224	0.290
Pre/Post	1	1.344	1.344	1.213	0.297
Gender	1	1.394	1.394	1.257	0.288
Age	1	2.504	2.503	2.259	0.164
DTC	1	0.073	0.073	0.066	0.802

Note. DF = degrees of freedom, DTC = days to contact, Sq = square.

Finally, a multiple linear regression was conducted with age, gender (m), days to contact and pre/post scores to predict patient satisfaction scores. Multiple linear regression was used to examine how much of the variance in satisfaction scores could be explained by the combination of predictor variables: age, male gender, and days to contact. The results of the regression was not significant: $F(4, 10) = 1.199$, $P > 0.370$, $R^2 = 0.324$. The 32.4% variability in the scores were explained by the regression by introducing age, gender (m), and days to contact.

DISCUSSION

At this institution, we were unable to show a statistically significant increase in the patient satisfaction scores with the new medication instructions. The manner in which the hospital surveyed and gathered information from the patient population restricted the ability to increase the sample size. Although there was insignificance in the results, it cannot be assumed that a larger sample size would not have shown significance. The project failed to meet the goal to increase patient satisfaction scores by 20%. Despite these results, the narcotic medication instructions provided to the patients were well received by the staff of the hospital. They viewed the instructions as concise, very well written, and chose to continue to use them after the project was completed. Although limited by a small sample size, our null findings do support other studies which have shown that patient satisfaction is a complex concept which makes it difficult to measure with confidence (Spooner, 2003). The manner in which the sample was surveyed could present a bias and cannot be applied to the entire population of the facility. This may have contributed to the results of the study because the volume of patients discharged with pain medication per month is well over 250. Therefore, surveying only 5 patients per month was not a representative sample.

The PDSA cycle was effective to guide and implement the project. The discussion of the project and analysis of the results are vital in the Act phase of this theoretical framework. Even though the results of the study did not show statistically significant changes in patient satisfaction, one may conclude that areas of the study can be adjusted or changed to, once again, start the cycle to obtain the desired effect. The

variables of the study need to be reexamined to determine if and what changes could be made to the study in order to increase patient satisfaction.

Patients discharged from the hospital received multiple pages of discharge instructions regarding self-care, disease management, surgical specific information, medication reconciliation forms and medication instructions. This was the situation during the study period. The hospital initiated a 12-page medication education pamphlet at the time of the study which provided duplicate information to the patient.

Patients are more apt to receive discharge instruction when their individualized needs have been evaluated prior to discharge (Bobay, Jerofke, Weiss, & Yakusheva, 2010). Nurses need to ensure they are evaluating each patient for their individual educational requirements and not assume that one discharge packet works for all patients. Nursing has an important role in whether or not discharge information is retained by the patient. Eliciting open ended or restatement during the discharge phase can provide inadequacies of education. In prior studies, nursing skills in delivering the discharge teaching was found to be a predictor of discharge readiness, more than the amount of information the patients received (Bobay et. al., 2010). This may have been a significant issue with the nursing staff of the hospital when they delivered the medication instructions and future research should ensure the skills of the nursing staff are evaluated. The education and communication skills of the nursing staff were not evaluated prior to project implementation. There are benefits to ensuring patients fully understand their discharge instructions. Multiple research studies have found a direct correlation to discharge instruction competence and reduced readmission rates.

Medication instructions can be delivered in many forms. The format to provide instructions on medication has been the focus of numerous research studies. The most effective format to educate patients was found with the use of multidisciplinary approaches. Pharmacist counseling showed a statistically significant increase in medication knowledge when compared to a control group who received instructions by standard discharge methods (Ponnusankar, Surulivelrajan, Anandamoorthy, & Suresh, 2004). Another study by Kerzman, Baron-Epel, and Toren (2005) stressed the importance of medication counseling prior to discharge and in the community at the time of prescription fulfillment. Unfortunately, including pharmacists in the discharge of short stay outpatient surgical patients would be a costly endeavor.

The level to which patients report their satisfaction has, in research, found to be related to multiple factors. As reported in a study by Maloney and Weiss (2008), patients who do not feel they received enough information will express dissatisfaction with their discharge instructions and their experiences after discharge. The study did not have control over how the patients were questioned regarding their satisfaction with medication instructions. It is possible that during the interview period, the interviewer and the patient exchanged words which may have affected the ability to capture the true satisfaction score with medication instructions.

Demographic variables have a profound effect on results of studies and therefore, collecting more demographic information, the more valid the information generated. This research study was limited to age and gender of the patient. Those two variables were not significant in affecting the patient's satisfaction score, at least not statistically. The American Psychological Association's publication manual stressed to need to

provide specific information about study participant's characteristics such as their racial, ethnic and socioeconomic status (Hammer, 2011).

Seven (35%) of the participants in this study were over the age of 65. Previous research regarding the educational needs of the geriatric population revealed geriatric patients have different discharge needs due to their increased likelihood of comorbidities, illness induced limitations, impaired mobility, fatigue, anxiety, cognitive impairment, hearing impairments, health literacy deficits, and living alone (Bobay et al., 2010). The medication instruction sheet used during the project was universal and special attention to geriatric needs, such as large font, was not utilized.

The gender of a patient effects how much and to what degree information is received. Research has found that females value the need for information about illness and treatment and tend to ask more medical questions than males (Maloney and Weiss, 2008). Though females desire more information, research also discovered that there was no significant correlation with the level of medication knowledge after discharge instructions between males and females (Kerzman et al., 2005). The lack of a statistically significant effect of gender on the patient satisfaction score restricts the ability to conclude if the gender of the patient had any effect on the results. To further study this subject, the researcher should collect more information than just age and gender to determine if any other demographic variables have an effect on patient satisfaction.

Recommendations for Practice

The introduction of simplified discharge medication instructions can provide simple, understandable, and useful information. Providing a simplified variation of the medication instruction sheet in multiple languages, font sizes, and, in conjunction with

pharmacist counseling, should be studied to evaluate patient's satisfaction with these changes. Gearing the medication instruction form to take into account the demographic variables of race, ethnicity, socio-economic status, gender, and age could affect satisfaction.

Project Limitations

A statistical sample needs to reach 25 in order to make assumptions from the results. This study had a pre and post sample of only 10 patients for each group. With a larger sample size, there could have been significant differences between the responses of patients of varying age, gender or days to contact. The sample may have been able to show an increase in satisfaction with medication instructions provided.

Another limitation of the study was the short duration of the project and data collection. Data was collected for only two months after the addition of the medication instructions. Given a larger sample size, the results could have potentially elicited statistically significant results with the pilot study.

The medication instructions were only provided in English. This limitation may have contributed to the low satisfactions scores. The hospital's ethnic groups include Hispanic, Asian, and European patients who may not have been able to read or understand the instructions in English. Without the ethnic demographic information from the hospital it was unknown if this was a factor that effected satisfaction.

During the time frame of the study, the hospital initiated a 12-page medication information booklet on all medications that was given to all patients upon discharge from the hospital. The initiation of this booklet may have affected the results of the study and overwhelmed the patient with various forms of the same medication information.

The presence of a third party company which conducted the interview in a scripted form was a limitation. The researcher had no control over the ability to elicit qualitative information from the patients interviewed.

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APPENDIX A

MEDICATION INSTRUCTIONS

NARCOTIC PAIN MEDICATION SIDE EFFECTS PATIENT INFORMATION SHEET

What are medication side effects?

Medication side effects are any effects a medication has on your body, other than the intended effects. Medication side effects may occur even when a medication is prescribed and taken properly.

How are medication side effects treated?

Some medication side effects are harmless and require no intervention at all. **All medication side effects that require intervention are treatable and should be reported promptly to your physician.** Some common side effects associated with pain medication along with preventative measures and/or treatments are listed below.

PAIN MEDICATION SIDE EFFECTS	PREVENTATIVE ACTION:
<i>Drowsiness/sedation</i>	Notify your physician as soon as possible if you experience this side effect. Your physician may do the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjust the medication dosage • Provide alternative methods of pain relief
<i>Constipation</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase activity • Increase fluid intake • Increase fiber/bulk in diets (fruit, vegetables, whole wheat bread) • Laxative (Sennokot, Colace)
<i>Nausea (associated with pain medication or in conjunction with constipation)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid taking on an empty stomach • Talk to your physician about anti-nausea drug or other medication

What can I do to prevent medication side effects?

In addition to the preventative measures listed above, be sure to do the following:

- Take your medication as prescribed.
- Avoid alcohol. It may interact with your pain medication and cause dangerous levels of sedation.
- Keep scheduled appointments with your physician for continued monitoring of your condition.
- Do not drive or operate machinery while on pain medication.

Remember, you will not reach your goal of adequate pain relief if side effects lead you to stop your pain medication or alter the dosage prescribed by your physician. Always call your physician to report any unpleasant medication side effects.

This is not an all-inclusive list of side effects: Consult with your Pharmacist when you fill your prescription.

APPENDIX B

TABLES OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL

Summary of Studies: Discharge Instructions

Purpose, Author(s), year	Design and Key Variables	Sample and setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To determine differences in INFO provided and the INFO needed by PTS. (Maloney & Weiss 2008).	Cross-sectional descriptive, comparative secondary analysis.	Urban tertiary-level Mid-western US general, medical and cardiac IP units, >18 years old, 115 PTS, 57% female, mean of 52.8 years old, 52% married.	QDTS discharge questionnaire, 24 item in 2 subscales of content and delivery of DC teaching. 4 hours prior to DC, descriptive statistics. PT characteristics, Hospitalization factors, quality of teaching.	PTS got more teaching than they needed indicated met and exceeded. PTS with more hospitalizations received more INFO.	Limitations: no Hispanic PTS in sample, using the QDTS to general. Using pre-existing data set, using PTS perception of need is not accurate to their true need. Notes: Standardized DC teaching plans with defined content increases knowledge of PTS. First hospitalization needs more INFO. Non-white reported more needs.
To evaluate PTS understanding of DC INSTs. (Zavala & Shaffer 2011)	Prospective, randomized, descriptive study.	49 PTS, >18 years old, discharged from Reston, Virginia ER over 5 WK timeframe. 66% F, mean age 48 years.	Follow-up telephone call one day after DC with data collection instrument. Demographic data: age, gender, chief complaint, diagnosis. Open ended questions: how are you doing today, do you have any questions? Confusion about DC INSTs.	31% needed clarification of the DC INSTs, 31% had poor comprehension of aftercare INSTs.	Limitations: small sample size, only English or Spanish PTS in study may have eliminated those with greatest difficulty in understanding DC INSTs. Conclusions: routine DC INSTs not sufficient for clear understanding by PTS. Notes: Creating specific DC INSTs can improve understanding.

Purpose, Author(s), year	Design and Key Variables	Sample and setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
<p>Comparison of structured verses standard PT EDU and the effect on PT SAT.</p> <p>(Ben-Morderchai et al., 2010)</p>	<p>Interventional prospective study, quasi-experimental, pretest-postest design.</p> <p>IV: Nurse education utilizing booklet of essential topics for structured DC.</p> <p>DV: PT SAT with DC INSTs.</p>	<p>Convenience sample, DCd orthopedic PTS from a hospital of unknown location.</p> <p>CG N=48 DCd between April 1, 2007 to May 31, 2007 standard DC INSTs.</p> <p>IG N=47 DC'd BTW June 1, 2007 to July 31, 2007.</p> <p>14-93 years old, mean 51.54 years, 59% M.</p>	<p>Telephone interview 6 weeks after DC by designated RN, pain questionnaire, SAT of care Likert scale questionnaire, standard and instrumental ADL Likert scale questionnaire.</p> <p>Hospitalization, pain management, functional status and compliance with follow-up visits.</p>	<p>No significant differences in demographic data, number of unplanned medical visits.</p> <p>IG had fewer pain complaints, higher follow-up visit compliance, higher SAT with nurse-PT communication and DC INSTs, and functional status.</p> <p>93% of IG had one or more follow-up visit with MD, 77% of CG.</p>	<p>Limitations: interviewer not blinded, small sample size.</p> <p>Conclusion: structured INSTs improve PT outcomes, SAT, pain control, self-care, and compliance with follow-up visits.</p> <p>Notes: example of structured DC EDU in study.</p>

Notes: BTW = Between, CG = Control Group, DC = Discharge, DV = Dependent Variable, EDU = Education, F = Female, IG = Intervention Group, INFO = Information, INST = Instruction, IP = Inpatient, IV = Independent Variable, M = Male, PT = Patient, PTS = Patients, QDTS = Quality of Discharge Teaching Scale, SAT = Satisfaction.

Summary of Studies: Medication Instructions

Purpose, Author(s), year	Design and Key Variables	Sample and setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
Does a structured DC interview increase MED knowledge? (Louis-Simonet et al., 2004)	Experimental Study, pre and post test, IG: structured DC INT with treatment card, CG: usual practice.	GenevaHOSP, 2 120 bed medical units, PTS prescribed >1 MED at DC, blinded patients, CG N = 439, EG N = 370.	Telephone survey one week after DC with standardized questions. MED recall, purpose of MED, SE.	Intervention increased K of DC MEDS (purpose, precautions, SE) and increased ACK of receipt of INST. K of SE decreased likelihood of stopping MED against physician order.	Limitations: non-randomized trial. Card itself may have increased K. Only studied MEDS PTS were already taking. Notes: structured INT at DC with review of MEDS increases K and ACK of receipt of INST. EDU of SE increased compliance.
To assess PT knowledge of MEDS after DC. (Kerzman et al., 2005)	Cross-sectional survey PT knowledge of MED, factors that increase knowledge.	6 IM units in Israel. PTS >45, >1 day in HOSP, DC with prescriptions, New MED N = 206, Previous MED N = 288.	Questionnaire measuring MEDS purpose, schedule, SE, tests needed and required lifestyle changes.	PTS need counseling regarding MED therapy. Only 40% received INST.	Limitations: only apply to hospitalized elderly. Not REP of population. Did not control counseling. Notes: verify K of MED prior to DC, provide written INST, Older PTS wanted MED INFO from physicians not nurses.
To evaluate if standardized ELEC DC INST with embedded MEDRECON will decrease RADM (Showalter et al., 2011)	Retrospective pre and post test, cohort study.	Penn State Medical Center, 501 bed academic hospital. >18 years old, Pre 2005-2006 N = 16,572, Post 2007-2008 N = 17,516.	Primary outcome of RADM within 30 days. ED visits within 30 days.	No decrease in RADMs or 30 day ED visits. Small statistically significant increase in RADM.	Limitations: No data on RADM to other HOSPs. No evaluation of understanding of DC INST. Pre and Post groups differed. Notes: ELEC imbedded MED INSTs alone does not effect a decrease in HOSP RADMs.
To explore the PT needs on INFO about MEDS at DC. (Borgsteede et al.,	Qualitative, IG = received counseling and MED RECON and	Netherlands, March through June 2007, 31 PTS from pulmonary, IM, and	Semi-structured INT, audio-taped. Data saturation achieved. Recurrent themes: basic	Most PTS wanted basic INFO. Did not want INFO on side effects. Algorithm provided	Limitations: Possible social desirable answers in response to HOSP care received, limited free expression.

Purpose, Author(s), year	Design and Key Variables	Sample and setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
2011)	INFO from pharmacist, CG = usual manner of EDU from nurses and doctors.	cardiology DPTs.	INFO, SE, alternatives, reactions.	regarding tailoring of INFO based on PTS request.	Notes: PTS more SAT with counseling of MEDS. Written and oral INSTs. Involve PT in determining their need of INFO.

Notes: ACK = Acknowledgement, CG = Control Group, DC = Discharge, DPT = Department, EDU = Education, ELEC = Electronic, HOSP = Hospital, IG = Interventional Group, IM = Internal Medicine, INFO = Information, INST = Instructions, INT = Interview, K = Knowledge, MED = Medication, MEDS = Medications, PT = Patient, PTS = Patients, RADM = Readmission, RECON = Reconciliation, REP = Representative, SAT = Satisfied, SE = Side Effects.

Summary of Studies: Patient Satisfaction

Purpose, Author(s), year	Design and Key Variables	Sample and setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To determine if the results of PT SAT surveys are attributed to the hospital, DPT or PT characteristics, to investigate the case mix variables when surveys are carried out. (Hekkert et al., 2009)	5-point Likert scale survey, retrospective, KV: SAT.	Netherlands, 2005, 8 academic and 18 general hospitals, selected 200 PTS randomly for each DPT, IP and OP, N=38,692 for OP, 27,919 for IP. 48% male, 42% > 60 y/o, 26% educated.	COPS survey by mail, PT SAT with admission procedure, nursing care, medical care, information, PT autonomy, DC and aftercare.	SAT scores determined at the PT level. Age, health status and EDU had an effect on SAT. Case mix must be taken into consideration when benchmarking hospitals.	Limitations: skewed high SAT caused by design. Unsatisfied more likely responded. Notes: PT characteristics of age, health status and EDU are important determinants of SAT. Older PTS score lower SAT. OP DPT's have higher rankings.

Notes: COPS = Core Questionnaire for Patient Satisfaction, DC = Discharge, DD = Demographic Data, DPT = Department, EDU = Education, HOSP = Hospital, INST = Instruction, KV = Key Variable, IP = Inpatients, OP = Outpatients, PT = Patient, PTS = Patients, Q = Questionnaire, SAT = Satisfaction.

Summary of Studies: Demographic Variables

Purpose, Author(s), year	Design and Key Variables	Sample and setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To determine differences in INFO provided and the INFO needed by PTS. (Maloney & Weiss 2008)	Cross-sectional descriptive, secondary analysis.	Mid-western US inpatient units, >18 years old, 115 PTS.	QDTS discharge questionnaire 4 hours prior to DC, descriptive statistics. Patient characteristics, Hospitalization factors, quality of teaching.	PTS got more teaching than they needed indicated met and exceeded. PTS with more hospitalizations received more information.	Limitations: using the QDTS to general. Using pre-existing DS, using PTS perception of need isn't accurate to their true need. Notes: Standardized DC teaching plans with defined content increases knowledge of PTS. First hospitalization needs more INFO. Non-white reported more needs.
To determine if the results of PT SAT surveys are attributed to the hospital, DPT or PT characteristics and to investigate the case mix variables when surveys are carried out. (Hekkert et al., 2009)	5 point Likert scale survey, retrospective, KV: SAT.	Netherlands, 2005, 8 academic and 18 general hospitals, selected 200 PTS randomly for each DPT, IP and OP, N=38,692 for OP, 27,919 for IP. 48% male, 42% > 60 y/o, 26% educated.	COPS survey by mail, PT SAT with admission procedure, nursing care, medical care, information, PT autonomy, DC, and aftercare.	SAT scores determined at the PT level. Age, health status and EDU had an effect on SAT. Case mix must be taken into consideration when benchmarking hospitals.	Limitations: skewed high SAT caused by design. Unsatisfied more likely responded. Notes: PT characteristics of age, health status and EDU are important determinants of SAT. Older PTS score lower SAT. OP DPT's have higher rankings.
Evaluate PT SAT at DC and 30 days after, identify predictive factors. (Lemos et al., 2009).	Cross-sectional, observational, prospective.	Portugal, day surgery unit, 2004-2005, university HOSP, 251 consecutive PTS, >15 years.	Q at DC by INT and 30 days later by TELE INT.	Higher SAT scores = better INFO, less pain, less infection, better surgical outcome, older more SAT.	Limitations: Q not validated. Notes: Older PTS higher SAT.

Notes. COPS = Core Questionnaire for Patient Satisfaction, DC = Discharge, DD = Demographic Data, DPT = Department, DS = Data Set, EDU = Education, HOSP = Hospital, INFO = Information, INST = Instruction, INT = Interview, KV = Key Variable, IP = Inpatients, OP = Outpatients, PT = Patient, PTS = Patients, Q = Questionnaire, SAT = Satisfaction, TELE = Telephone.

